

The Essence of Verilog (Supplementary Material)

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This is the supplementary material of our paper: “The Essence of Verilog: A Tractable and Tested Operational Semantics for Verilog” in PACMPL (OOPSLA 2023) [1]. It provides a comprehensive specification of λ_V ’s syntax and semantics rules, as well as to introduce the extensive features that were only briefly outlined in Table 1 of our paper due to space limitations. In Section 1, we explain these features, address potential pitfalls, and present ideas for modeling them in λ_V . These features include extensions in values and types (Section 1.1), repeat and named event control (Section 1.2), selects as left values of assignments (Section 1.3), procedural continuous assignment (Section 1.4), advanced flow control (Section 1.5), modules (Section 1.6), tasks and functions (Section 1.7 and Section 1.8), and gate-level modeling (Section 1.9). The complete list of λ_V ’s syntax and semantic rules can be found in Appendix A.

1 Extension

1.1 Extended Values and Types

In our paper, we mentioned that while bit vectors are sufficient to model any data in a Verilog program, we also introduce some extended types and values for pragmatic convenience, including

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```

1 wire a0, a1, a2, a3;      1 wire a[4];              1 wire a[4];
2 wire b0, b1, b2, b3;      2 wire b[4];              2 wire b[4];
3 assign b0 = a0;           3                           3 assign b[0] = a[0];
4 assign b1 = a1;           4 genvar i;               4 assign b[1] = a[1];
5 assign b2 = a2;           5 for (i = 0; i < 4; i = i+1) 5 assign b[2] = a[2];
6 assign b3 = a3;           6   assign b[i] = a[i];    6 assign b[3] = a[3];

```

(a) Connect wires by hand. (b) Connect wires by genloop. (c) Elaborated wire connections.

Figure 1: Connect four wires using different features.

real numbers, string literals, and arrays. The syntax of those types and values are defined below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau &\in \textit{Type} && := \tau_b \mid [\tau_b; sz] \\
\tau_b &\in \textit{BaseType} && := \textit{bsz} \mid \textit{real} \mid \textit{string} \\
sz &\in \textit{Size} && = \mathbb{N} - \{0\} \\
bv &\in \textit{BitVec} && = \{\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}\}^+ \\
v &\in \textit{Value} && = \textit{BitVec} \cup \mathbb{R} \cup \{(\textit{chars})\}^* \cup (\textit{BitVec} \mapsto \textit{Value})
\end{aligned}$$

These definitions are similar to those used in semantics for software languages, and no further explanation is needed.

The interesting part is that we treat Verilog’s variable arrays and nets arrays differently. For a variable array, we transform it into a λ_V variable of array type, but for a net array, we desugar it into individual nets.

This approach works because net arrays are designed to group nets for writing succinct and scalable code rather than for storing large-scale data. Consider the example of connecting four pairs of wires: without net arrays, the resulting code would be lengthy and cumbersome (as shown in Figure 1a). By contrast, using net arrays along with a generate construct (as shown in Figure 1b) makes the code far more concise and scalable. However, because the generate construct is a meta-programming feature, during the elaboration step at the beginning of compilation, the code is transformed into the form shown in 1c, with only individual nets left. Although they are represented in the form of array accesses, the indices are always constants.

Another piece of evidence supporting our approach is the fact that if an array access occurs as the left value of a continuous assignment (e.g., `assign a[i] = 1`), the index i must be a constant. This is because continuous assignments should determine which net they will drive before runtime. Without this constraint, it is impossible to desugar net arrays in continuous assignments. (Note that net arrays cannot occur on the left-hand side of procedural assignments.)

One might wonder how to desugar net array accesses that occur on the right-hand side of an assignment, such as $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{a}[i]$, where \mathbf{x} and i are variables and \mathbf{a} is a net array of size 4. The solution is to concatenate the net array as a single vector and then extract the indexed part using the select operators. For example, the previous example can be desugared as follows: $\mathbf{x} = \text{bitSelect}(\text{concat}(\mathbf{a}[0], \mathbf{a}[1], \mathbf{a}[2], \mathbf{a}[3]), i)$.

Therefore, we consider that net arrays are more of a static feature that is better to be treated as syntactic sugar. In contrast, variable arrays are designed to model memories and are better treated as primitive values in our semantics. Some might argue that variable array accesses can be desugared easily even when the indices are non-constant variables. However, we believe that the resulting desugared code would be unnatural. Additionally, it is not difficult to define array semantics for variables.

Taking all of these factors into account, we model variable arrays as primitive values in our

semantics and desugar net arrays. This desugaring approach simplifies the code related to net assignments.

1.2 Timing Control

In this section, we talk about repeat event control and named event control that are not introduced in our paper.

1.2.1 Repeat Event Control

In Verilog, the syntax of repeat event control is `repeat (n) cev` and means the event control c_{ev} should be satisfied n times. For example, the codes below are functionally equivalent:

<pre> 1 a = repeat(3) 2 @(posedge clk) b;</pre>	<pre> 1 begin 2 temp = b; 3 @(posedge clk); 4 @(posedge clk); 5 @(posedge clk) a = temp; 6 end</pre>
---	--

The pitfall of repeat event control in Verilog is that previous semantics mistakenly treated it as syntactic sugar, similar to transforming the above code on the left to the code on the right. However, this approach does not apply to repeat event controls inner nonblocking assignments (e.g., `a <= repeat(3) @(posedge clk) b;`) because the desugared code can block the process and therefore is not semantically equivalent to the original one. (Recall that nonblocking assignments do not block a process)

To support repeat event controls, we transform them into stateful conditions $(n, cond, cond)$ by the rules below:

$$\frac{e, \Sigma \rightarrow^* bv, \Sigma' \quad \neg(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z} \in bv) \quad n = \text{int}(bv) \quad n \leq 0}{\text{repeat } e \ c_{ev}, \Sigma \Downarrow_c \checkmark, \Sigma'}$$

$$\frac{e, \Sigma \rightarrow^* bv, \Sigma' \quad \neg(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z} \in bv) \quad n = \text{int}(bv) \quad n > 0 \quad c_{ev}, \Sigma' \Downarrow_c \text{cond}, \Sigma''}{\text{repeat } e \ c_{ev}, \Sigma \Downarrow_c (n, \text{cond}, \text{cond}), \Sigma''}$$

where the $cond$ is the condition of the event control c_{ev} in `repeat n cev` and n records how many times the $cond$ still need to be satisfied. The $cond$ occurs twice because we need to extend the `onEvent()` function as below:

$$\text{onEvent}((n, \text{cond}, \text{cond}'), ev) = (\text{cond}'' = \checkmark) ? (n - 1 = 0 ? \checkmark : (n - 1, \text{cond}, \text{cond})), \\ : (n, \text{cond}, \text{cond}''), \text{ where } \text{onEvent}(\text{cond}', ev) = \text{cond}''$$

Note that the stateful condition causes difficulty in extending repeat event controls from previous works.

1.2.2 Named Event

In Verilog, we can declare a named event `event ev;` and use a named event control `@ev` to guard a statement, waiting for it to be triggered by the statement `-> ev.`

However, as mentioned by our paper, named event control has ambiguity in syntax according to the specification, which is given as follows:

```

event_control ::= @ hierarchical_event_identifier
               | @ ( event_expression )
event_expression ::= expression
                  | posedge expression
                  | negedge expression
                  | event_expression or event_expression
                  | event_expression , event_expression

```

where the `hierarchical_event_identifier` refers to a named event in the program.

According to the syntax, a named event shall not be surrounded by brackets when used in an `event_control` because the production of event expression does not allow it. However, there is a case in Section 18.1.6 (page 329) of the specification that contradicts this rule. The related code snippet is as follows:

```

1 event do_dump;
2 initial @(do_dump)
3   forever #10000 $dumpall;

```

In this case, it can be seen that the named event `do_dump` in the event control is surrounded by brackets, which goes against the defined syntax.

To make λ_V more robust, we design λ_V to allow named events to be involved in event expressions. As a result, the extended syntax for named events is as follows:

$$\eta \in EventExpr := id_{ev} \mid e \mid posedge e \mid negedge e \mid \eta \text{ or } \eta$$

where id_{ev} represents a named event. Other semantic rules related to named events are easy to understand, which can be found in Appendix A.7.

1.3 Selects as Left Values

We only described the scenario using a simple identifier as the left value in the paper to avoid the tedious rules that would be introduced when array accesses and bit selects occur on the left-hand side of assignments. And of course, Full- λ_V does support these features, and they can be found in semantic rules related to assignments in Appendix A.9. Since array accesses as left values are common in software languages, we will focus only on how to model bit selects as left values in this section.

Verilog has bit-select and part-select operators that allow sub-parts of a bit vector to be extracted, which resemble slices in many software languages. They are used like $id[i]$ and $id[i:j]$, where the id is a bit vector. We focus on bit-selects for simplicity, but the mechanism also applies to part-selects.

When bit-selects are used on the right-hand side of assignments, they can be easily modeled by defining a λ_V primitive function called “bitSelect”. If they are used on the left-hand side of blocking assignments (e.g., $x[i] = bv$), they can be handled by desugaring the assignment as $x = bitSet(x, i, bv)$. The `bitSet()` function can be defined based on primitive operators, which would return a new bit vector value bv' whose i -th bit is replaced by bv .

However, when bit-selects are used on the left-hand side of nonblocking assignments and continuous assignments, desugaring is not sufficient to handle them. Consider the following two failure cases when trying to desugar the left-hand side part-selects:

1. Suppose that we have a variable x whose initial value is **0010** and two nonblocking assignments $x[0] \leftarrow 1; x[1] \leftarrow 0$. The correct resulting value of x must be **0001**. However, if we desugar the nonblocking assignments as $x \leftarrow \text{bitSet}(x, 0, 1); x \leftarrow \text{bitSet}(x, 1, 0)$, scheduling two update events $(x, \mathbf{0011})$ and $(x, \mathbf{0000})$ in order, the final value of x will be **0000** instead of **0001**.
2. Given a continuous assignment **assign** $x[i] = 1$, if it is desugared as **assign** $x = \text{bitSet}(x, i, 1)$, all bit of x except the i -th bit are connected to themselves according to the semantics of continuous assignments, forming a loop in the combinational logic.

The root cause of these failures in desugaring is that old values of the unselected parts on the left-hand side are retained in the update events scheduled by non-blocking and continuous assignments, which will override the new values of those unselected parts assigned by other assignments before those update events are carried out.

To address this issue, we support part-selects as left values in λ_V , which have syntax as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 e_l \in LExpr & := id([e])?([e:e])? \\
 v_l \in LValue & := id([v])?([v:v])? \\
 s \in Stmt & := \dots | e_l = e | \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

At runtime, the left expression e_l at the left-hand side of assignment $e_l = e$ will be evaluated to a left value v_l used to access the target of the assignment.

This new mechanism does not require new semantic rules, but it does necessitate some meta-functions for bit-level analyses in assignments. Readers can refer to semantic rules related to assignments in Appendix A.9 for more details.

1.4 Procedural Continuous Assignments

As mentioned in the paper, procedural continuous assignment enables programmers to attach or detach continuous assignments at runtime. The pitfall in procedural continuous assignments is that they have different priorities and continuous assignments with higher priority can override those with lower priority assignments, making it harder to handle the resolution on nets and needing careful analysis.

Note that the concept of priority is not original in the specification but is extracted from its probe descriptions.

Take the example below to illustrate the semantics of procedural continuous assignments:

```

1 wor [2:0] a;
2 assign a = 3'b001;
3 assign a = 3'b010;
4 initial begin
5     #1; $display("%b", a);
6     force a = 3'b100;
7     #1; $display("%b", a);
8     force a = 3'b000;
9     #1; $display("%b", a);
10    release a;
11    #1; $display("%b", a);
12 end

```

where **a** is declared as a **wor** net, meaning if it has multiple drivers, the final value would be resolved by applying bitwise or on all the drivers. Check the output of the four **\$display** statement, we have

- (1) **a** is driven by two continuous assignments each with **3'b001** and **3'b010**, which would be resolved into **3'b011** in this case. And the first **\$display** would print **011**.

- (2) A force statement would overlap all the continuous assignment drivers since it has a higher priority. So the second `$display` should print 100 rather than 111.
- (3) Another force statement would overlap the previous one though they have the same priority. So in this case, the third `$display` would print 000.
- (4) Finally the `release` statement would cancel all the force statements driving `a`, and the two normal continuous assignments on line 2 and line 3 recover to take effect. Again, the fourth `$display` would print 011.

In λ_V , we specify the syntax of procedural continuous assignments as below:

$$s \in Stmt := \text{assign } v_l = e \text{ with } pr \mid \text{deassign } v_l \text{ with } pr \mid \dots$$

where pr stands for the priority of the statement. We conclude from the specification that procedural continuous assignments with leading keyword `force` and `release` are of priority 2; and those with `assign` and `deassign` are of priority 1. Relevant semantics rules can be found in [A.9.4](#).

Besides this, other semantic rules should be modified in response. For example, in rules related to blocking assignments, we need to introduce a resolve function for possible procedural continuous assignments that may drive the variable on the left-hand side of the blocking assignment. The modified rule is:

$$\frac{v_r = \text{resolve}(v_l, v, \alpha, \kappa, \sigma) \quad v_r \neq \text{load}(\sigma, v_l) \quad \sigma' = \text{store}(\sigma, v_l, v_r) \quad \beta' = \text{activate}(\beta, (\sigma, \sigma')) \quad u'_{nb} = \text{trigger}(u_{nb}, (\sigma, \sigma'))}{v_l = v, \sigma, \beta, u_{nb}, sig \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \sigma', \beta', u'_{nb}, sig \cup \text{signal}(\alpha, v_l)}$$

1.5 Advanced Flow Control

As we have mentioned in our paper, Verilog supports rich flow control features, including fork-join blocks and disable statements. However, extending the core rules of previous work to support these features is challenging. In this section, we explore the complexities of these features and demonstrate how Full- λ_V can successfully handle them, where previous work has fallen short.

1.5.1 Fork-Join

The fork-join blocks in Verilog is surrounded by keywords `fork-join` rather than `begin-end`, meaning every statement in the block shall execute concurrently and the delay controls involved shall be aligned to the simulation time of the block. This feature essentially requires the ability of a language to create and wait processes at runtime. For λ_V , it can be easily accommodated by the parallel composition statement ($s_0 \parallel s_1$), but previous work is hard to extend to provide such an ability.

1.5.2 Disable

Verilog provides labels to name a lexical scope and disable statements with the syntax of `disable label` to make control flows jump out of some named lexical scope. There are two possible usages: a process uses the statement to disable its own lexical scope, resulting in it jumping out of that scope; and a process uses the statement to disable other processes' lexical scope, resulting in other processes jumping out of that lexical scope.

In λ_V , we model such semantics using the statement `label{s}` and `disable label`. The `label{s}` creates a scope identified by `label` and embraces a statement `s` into it. If a process P is executing

statements in a *label*'s scope, we say the *label* is enabled by *P*. Assuming a *label* is enabled by *P*, and a process *Q* is executing the disable statement “**disable label**”, the process *P* will immediately jump out of the *label*'s scope to execute the next statement following the *label*{*s*}. *Q* can be the process *P* itself. If so, the code executed by *P* may look like *label*{...; **disable label**;...} and this code works like throwing and catching exceptions or break label statements in Java.

We extend λ_v by these features and give a formal specification. First is the syntax:

$$\begin{aligned} (Label) \quad label & := \dots \\ (Stmt) \quad s & := \dots \mid label\{s\} \mid \mathbf{disable} \quad label \mid s \mathbf{with} \quad label \end{aligned}$$

where “*s with label*” is used internally.

The configuration is extended by

$$conf := (\dots, \ell)$$

where ℓ is a set of enabled labels. Note that the definition of Σ is also extended. You can refer to [A.8.3](#) for the semantic rules.

1.6 Modules

```

module counter(                                     wire clk;
  input wire clk,                                  // Assume a clock generator.
  output reg [3:0] state                           wire [3:0] x, y, z;
);
always @(posedge clk)                             counter c1(clk, x);
  if (state == 9) state <= 0;                     counter c2(clk, y);
  else state <= state + 1;                         assign z = x + y;
endmodule

```

(a) A counter wrapped in a module.

(b) Two counter instances.

Figure 2: Example of a module and its instantiation.

In Verilog, modules provide a way to reuse hardware description code. For instance, suppose we need to describe a digital circuit that involves adding the outputs of two counters. We can encapsulate the code for the counter in Figure 2(c) of our paper within a module called `counter`, as shown in Figure 2a, where the header “`module counter(input clk, output state)`” declares the module name and its input and output ports. Then, we can instantiate the `counter` module twice, as shown in Figure 2b. When the module is instantiated as `counter c1(clk, x)`, for example, the input port `clk` and the output port `state` inside the module instance `c1` are connected to the nets or variables `clk` and `x` outside the instance, respectively.

However, λ_V does not have module structures. Instead, we inline Verilog modules to simplify the structures of λ_V , similar to inline functions in software languages. When inlining modules, we must pay attention to ports of inout type. Commonly, if the port direction is `input` or `output`, the connection is transformed into a continuous assignment from the source to the sink. However, if the port direction is `inout`, the source and the sink are treated as *aliases*. We replace all occurrences of their identifiers with a new unique identifier.

1.7 Tasks and Functions

Tasks and functions are designed to reuse control flows in Verilog. A function has one or more input arguments but only one return value and is syntactically restricted to model combinational logic.

A task can have input and output ports like a module do, but the ports are connected by blocking assignments rather than continuous assignments. Because there are no restrictions on what a task can do, it can model sequential logic in addition to combinational logic.

Basically, the variables in tasks and functions are allocated statically unless they are declared with an `automatic` keyword, in which case they are allocated on a stack. The automatic tasks and functions are not synthesizable and are seldom used in pure Verilog, so we don't model them in λ_V . In this section, we only focus on static tasks and functions.

The static tasks can be directly inlined on its call site with a few additional argument-passing assignments. Here is an example:

```

1 module main ();
2   reg v, w, x, y, z;
3
4   initial
5     foo(v, w, x, y, z);
6
7   task foo (input a, b, inout c, output d, e);
8     begin
9       ... // statements that perform the work of the task
10    end
11  endtask
12 endmodule

```

After inlining, it would look like

```

1 module main ();
2   reg v, w, x, y, z;
3   reg _tmp1 , _tmp2 , _tmp3 ;
4   reg foo_a , foo_b , foo_c , foo_d , foo_e ;
5
6   initial begin : main_foo
7     _tmp1 = v; _tmp2 = w; _tmp3 = x;
8     // pass arguments in
9     foo_a = _tmp1 ; foo_b = _tmp2 ; foo_c = _tmp3 ;
10
11     ... // statements that perform the work of the task
12
13     // pass results out
14     x = foo_c ; y = foo_d ; z = foo_e ;
15   end
16 endmodule

```

However, we do not inline functions. Instead, we add a new expression structure $e ::= \dots \mid \text{do } s \text{ return } e$ into λ_V in implementation to support function calls. This structure allows a statement to be an expression in a limited way and its evaluation rule is as follows:

$$\frac{s, \Sigma \rightarrow^* \text{skip}, \Sigma'}{\text{do } s \text{ return } e, \Sigma \hookrightarrow e, \Sigma'}$$

Now a function call in Verilog

```

1 module main ();
2   reg a;
3   wire x;
4   assign x = 1 + foo(a);
5   function foo (input p);
6     if (p) foo = p | 1;
7     else foo = p ^ 1;
8   endfunction
9 endmodule

```

can be desugared into λ_V as

```
1 wire x, a;
2 var foo, foo.p;
3 assign x = 1 + (do
4     foo.p = a;
5     if (foo.p) foo = foo.p | 1;
6     else foo = foo.p ^ 1;
7     return foo);
```

One may argue this language structure is unnecessary since a function only models combinational logic so there should be an equivalent one-line expression for it. However, suppose there is a function $f(x)$ with side effects, which would evaluate to different values y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots each time called with x . In this case, the multiple concatenations $\{4\{f(x)\}\}$ should be equivalent to $\{y_1, y_1, y_1, y_1\}$. To achieve this, the interpreter needs to introduce a temporary variable storing y_1 – which can only be achieved by the do-return-like structure, if not introducing an assignment $tmp = f(x)$ that may influence the scheduling.

1.8 System Tasks and Functions

System tasks and functions are provided as library functions in software languages and are commonly used to develop test benches. However, not all system tasks and functions are frequently used in practice. To avoid unnecessary implementation effort, we have only implemented commonly-used tasks and functions, such as `$display` and `$random`. Details of these engineering implementation can be found in our artifact [2].

1.9 Gate-Level Modeling

Verilog enables instantiating logic gates including the basic gates such as AND, OR, and NOT gates and three-state gates such as BUFIF and NOTIF. They are desugared into equivalent continuous assignments in λ_V .

For example, the former type of gates can be replaced by continuous assignment with logical expressions as below

```
and gate_1(a, b, c);    assign a = b & c;
```

and the latter type of gates can be replaced by continuous assignment with conditional expressions as below

```
bufif1 gate_2(a, b, c);    assign a = c ? buf(b) : z;
```

A Full Specification

A.1 Syntax

$p \in Program$	$:= \epsilon \mid \iota; p$
$\iota \in Item$	$:= k \ id:bsz \mid \text{var } id:\tau \mid \text{assign } c_d? \ v_l = e \mid \text{proc } s$
$k \in NetKind$	$:= \text{wire} \mid \text{wor} \mid \text{wand} \mid \dots$
$\tau \in Type$	$:= \tau_b \mid [\tau_b; sz]$
$\tau_b \in BaseType$	$:= \text{bsz} \mid \text{real} \mid \text{string}$
$sz \in Size$	$= \mathbb{N}^+$
$bv \in BitVec$	$= \{\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}\}^+$
$v \in Value$	$= BitVec \cup \mathbb{R} \cup \{(\text{chars})^*\} \cup (BitVec \mapsto Value)$
$id \in Id$	$= \{(\text{symbols})\}$
$e \in Expr$	$:= v \mid id \mid id[e] \mid op_m(e_1, \dots, e_m) \mid \text{do } s \ \text{return } e$
$e_l \in LExpr$	$:= id([e])?([e:e])?$
$v_l \in LValue$	$:= id([v])?([v:v])?$
$c \in TimingCtrl$	$:= c_{ev} \mid c_d \mid \text{repeat } e \ c_{ev}$
$c_{ev} \in EventCtrl$	$:= \mathcal{O}(\eta)$
$c_d \in DelayCtrl$	$:= \#e$
$\eta \in EventExpr$	$:= id_{ev} \mid e \mid \text{posedge } e \mid \text{negedge } e \mid \eta \ \text{or } \eta$
$s \in Stmt$	$:= \text{skip} \mid s; s \mid s \parallel s \mid$ $e_l = e \mid e_l = c \ e \mid e_l \leftarrow e \mid e_l \leftarrow c \ e \mid$ $c \ s \mid \rightarrow id_{ev} \mid$ $\text{assign } v_l = e \ \text{with } pr \mid \text{deassign } v_l \ \text{with } pr \mid$ $\text{if } e \ \text{then } s \ \text{else } s \mid \text{while } e \ \text{then } s \mid$ $\text{label } s \mid \text{disable } label \mid$ $s \ \text{with } label \mid \text{blocked } pid$
$label \in Label$	$= \{(\text{symbols})\}$
$pr \in Priority$	$= \mathbb{N}$
$pid \in ProcId$	$= \{(\text{symbols})\}$
$aid \in AssignId$	$= \{(\text{symbols})\}$

A.2 Configuration

$$conf := (s, \sigma, \beta, u_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha, u_\alpha, sig, \ell, t)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
s &\in \text{Stmt}, \\
\sigma &: (\text{Id} \cup \text{AssignId}) \mapsto \text{Value}, \\
\beta &: \text{ProcId} \mapsto \text{Cond}, \\
\text{Cond} &:= \text{EventExpr} \cup \mathbb{N} \cup (\mathbb{N}^+ \times \text{Cond} \times \text{Cond}) \cup \{\checkmark\} \\
u_{nb} &\subseteq (\text{Id} \times \text{BitVec} \times \text{Cond})^* \\
\kappa &: \text{Id} \mapsto \text{NetKind}, \\
\alpha &: \text{AssignId} \mapsto (\text{LValue} \times \text{Expr} \times \text{DelayControl}_\perp \times \text{Priority}), \\
u_\alpha &: \text{AssignId} \mapsto (\text{LValue} \times \text{Value} \times \text{Cond}), \\
\text{sig} &\subseteq \text{AssignId}, \\
\ell &: \text{Label} \mapsto \mathbb{N}^+, \\
t &\in \mathbb{N}.
\end{aligned}$$

Related mathematics annotation:

$$\square_\perp := \square \cup \{\perp\}. \quad (\perp \text{ can be interpreted as the null in programming languages}).$$

Σ denotes all but the first element of conf . “ $\Sigma.\text{name}$ ” projects Σ to the element named name . “ $\Sigma[\text{name} \mapsto v]$ ” replace the name element by a new value v . For example:

$$\Sigma.\beta = \beta, \text{ where } \Sigma = (\dots, \beta, \dots).$$

$$\Sigma[\beta \mapsto v] = (\dots, v, \dots), \text{ where } \Sigma = (\dots, \beta, \dots).$$

Note that the sig set in the configuration is not introduced in our paper. It is used to simplify continuous-assignments-related semantic rules by recording all the aids of signaled assign items, which mainly replaces the usage of function $\text{genUpdEv}()$ in our paper. The related rules can be found in Appendix A.9. In addition, during preprocessing, all assign items add their aids to the sig set to signal themselves for setting an initial value.

A.3 Preprocessing

Before defining reduction relations on configurations, we should first transform a λ_V program p into an initial configuration conf using $p \rightarrow_{pp} \text{conf}$ defined below.

$$\text{preprocess}(p) = \text{conf} \quad \text{iff} \quad p, (\text{skip}, \{\}, \{\}, \epsilon, \{\}, \{\}, \{\}, \emptyset, \{\}, 0) \rightarrow_{pp}^* \epsilon, \text{conf}.$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\sigma' = \sigma[id \mapsto \text{defVal}(k, \tau)] \quad \kappa' = \kappa[id \mapsto k]}{k \text{ id} : \tau; p, (\dots, \sigma, \dots, \kappa, \dots) \rightarrow_{pp} p, (\dots, \sigma', \dots, \kappa', \dots)} \\
\frac{\sigma' = \sigma[id \mapsto \text{defVal}(\text{var}, \tau)]}{\text{var id} : \tau; p, (\dots, \sigma, \dots) \rightarrow_{pp} p, (\dots, \sigma', \dots)} \\
\frac{\text{aid} = \text{newId}() \quad \alpha' = \alpha[\text{aid} \mapsto (id, e, c_d, 0)]}{\text{assign } c_d \text{ id} = e; p, (\dots, \alpha, \dots, \text{sig}, \dots) \rightarrow_{pp} p, (\dots, \alpha', \dots, \text{sig} \cup \{\text{aid}\}, \dots)}
\end{array}$$

$$\frac{aid = \text{newId()} \quad \alpha' = \alpha[aid \mapsto (id, e, \perp, 0)]}{\text{assign } id = e; p, (\dots, \alpha, \dots, sig, \dots) \rightarrow_{pp} p, (\dots, \alpha', \dots, sig \cup \{aid\}, \dots)}$$

$$\frac{}{\text{proc } s; p, (s', \dots) \rightarrow_{pp} p, (s \parallel s', \dots)}$$

defVal() returns the default value for a given kind and type. It is defined as

$$\text{defVal}(\text{var}, \tau) = \begin{cases} 0.0 & \tau = \text{real} \\ \perp & \tau = \text{string} \\ \mathbf{x}^{sz} & \tau = \text{bsz} \\ \{i \mapsto \text{defVal}(\text{var}, \tau'_i) \mid i = 0, 1, \dots, sz - 1\} & \tau = [\tau'_i; sz] \end{cases}$$

$$\text{defVal}(k, \text{bsz}) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{x}^{sz} & k = \text{trireg} \\ \mathbf{z}^{sz} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

A.4 Schedule Semantics

$$\frac{conf \rightarrow conf'}{conf \xrightarrow{v} conf'}$$

$$\frac{conf \not\rightarrow \quad conf \xrightarrow{0} conf'}{conf \xrightarrow{v} conf'}$$

$$\frac{conf \not\rightarrow \quad conf \xrightarrow{0} \quad conf \xrightarrow{nb} conf'}{conf \xrightarrow{v} conf'}$$

$$\frac{conf \not\rightarrow \quad conf \xrightarrow{0} \quad conf \xrightarrow{nb} \quad conf \xrightarrow{1} conf'}{conf \xrightarrow{v} conf'}$$

A.5 Context

Different from our paper, we use Felleisen-Hieb-Style Semantics [3] to help simplify our semantic rules below. In operational semantics, the semantic rules for a reduction relation on configurations such as $s, \Sigma \rightarrow s', \Sigma'$ are commonly defined based on all possible structures of the statement s . (Recall that Σ represents all but the first element in $conf$.) The Felleisen-Hieb style of small-step semantics decomposes s into two parts: the redex, which is the minimum structure being focused on (e.g., the expression or statement to be executed), and the context, which is the remaining structure. The decomposed s is denoted as $\mathcal{S}[e_r]$ or $\mathcal{S}[s_r]$. This approach only requires defining a new reduction relation on the redex (e.g., $s_r, \Sigma \hookrightarrow s'_r, \Sigma'$) that has much fewer structures than s , and then inducing the $s, \Sigma \rightarrow s', \Sigma'$ using the rule below. Note that the discussion also applies to expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E} \in \text{ExprCtx} & := [] \mid id[\mathcal{E}] \mid op_m(v_1, \dots, \mathcal{E}, \dots, e_m) \\ \mathcal{E}_l \in \text{LErrCtx} & := id[\mathcal{E}] ([e:e])? \mid id([v])? [\mathcal{E}:e] \mid id([v])? [v:\mathcal{E}] \\ \mathcal{S} \in \text{StmtCtx} & := [] \mid \mathcal{S}; s \mid \mathcal{S} \parallel s \mid s \parallel \mathcal{S} \mid \\ & \quad \mathcal{E}_l = e \mid v_l = \mathcal{E} \mid \mathcal{E}_l \leftarrow e \mid v_l \leftarrow \mathcal{E} \mid \\ & \quad \mathcal{E}_l = c \ e \mid v_l = c \ \mathcal{E} \mid \mathcal{E}_l \leftarrow c \ e \mid v_l \leftarrow c \ \mathcal{E} \mid \\ & \quad \text{if } \mathcal{E} \text{ then } s \text{ else } s \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{e, \Sigma \hookrightarrow e', \Sigma'}{\mathcal{S}[e], \Sigma \rightarrow \mathcal{S}[e'], \Sigma'} \quad \frac{s, \Sigma \hookrightarrow s', \Sigma'}{\mathcal{S}[s], \Sigma \rightarrow \mathcal{S}[s'], \Sigma'}$$

A.6 Expression

Because the expressions in Full- λ_V have side effects on other elements in configurations, we use the reduction relation $e, \Sigma \hookrightarrow e, \Sigma'$ to evaluate them instead of $\llbracket e \rrbracket \sigma$ used in our paper.

$$\frac{}{id, \sigma \hookrightarrow \sigma(id), \sigma}$$

$$\frac{}{id[v], \sigma \hookrightarrow \sigma(id)(v), \sigma}$$

$$\frac{}{op_m(v_1, \dots, v_m) \hookrightarrow \delta_m(op_m, v_1, \dots, v_m)}$$

$$\frac{s, \Sigma \rightarrow^* \text{skip}, \Sigma'}{\text{do } s \text{ return } e, \Sigma \hookrightarrow e, \Sigma'}$$

All op in λ_V are listed below. The semantics of operators are defined by δ_m which maps an operator and its operands to some value and you can refer to our artifact [2] for its implementation-specific details.

Kind	Name	Remark
Arithmetic	<code>add</code> , <code>sub</code> , <code>mul</code> , <code>pow</code> , <code>upow</code> <code>sdiv</code> , <code>udiv</code> , <code>srem</code> , <code>urem</code>	Operators with an ‘s’ prefix mean they treat the operands as signed ones. And operators with a ‘u’ prefix mean they treat the operands as unsigned ones.
Logical	<code>and</code> , <code>or</code> , <code>not</code> , <code>xor</code> , <code>xnor</code> , <code>buf</code> , <code>rand</code> , <code>ror</code> , <code>rxor</code>	Operators with an ‘r’ prefix mean they are reductive operators that apply the logical operator bit by bit on its only operand and finally return a one-bit result.
Relation	<code>slt</code> , <code>sgt</code> , <code>sleq</code> , <code>sgeq</code> , <code>ult</code> , <code>ugt</code> , <code>uleq</code> , <code>ugeq</code> , <code>eq</code> , <code>neq</code> , <code>zeq</code> , <code>xeq</code> , <code>equiv</code>	<code>zeq</code> neglects z when comparing its operands. <code>xeq</code> neglects x when comparing its operands. <code>equiv</code> demands bit-level equivalence.
Extension	<code>zext</code> , <code>sext</code> , <code>toBitVector</code> , <code>toReal</code>	<code>zext</code> extends operand by adding prefix zero. <code>sext</code> extends operand by adding the sign bit of the original value.
Select	<code>partSelect</code> , <code>indexedSelect</code>	They correspond to Verilog’s <code>x[c:d]</code> and <code>x[i]</code> respectively.
Condition	<code>condition</code>	The <code>a?b:c</code> operator in Verilog.
Concatenate	<code>concat</code>	The <code>{a, b}</code> operator in Verilog.

Table 1: Primitive Functions

A.7 Timing Control

A.7.1 Condition

Timing controls are evaluated to conditions. Because they may have side effects, we use a reduction relation $c, \Sigma \Downarrow_c \text{cond}, \Sigma'$ to define it.

$$\begin{array}{c} \overline{\text{@}(\eta), \Sigma \Downarrow_c \eta, \Sigma} \\ \frac{e, \Sigma \rightarrow^* bv, \Sigma' \quad \Delta = (\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z} \in bv) ? 0 : \text{uint}(bv)}{\#e, \Sigma \Downarrow_c (\Sigma.t + \Delta), \Sigma'} \\ \frac{e, \Sigma \rightarrow^* bv, \Sigma' \quad \neg(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z} \in bv) \quad n = \text{int}(bv) \quad n \leq 0}{\text{repeat } e \ c_{ev}, \Sigma \Downarrow_c \checkmark, \Sigma'} \\ \frac{e, \Sigma \rightarrow^* bv, \Sigma' \quad \neg(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z} \in bv) \quad n = \text{int}(bv) \quad n > 0 \quad c_{ev}, \Sigma' \Downarrow_c \text{cond}, \Sigma''}{\text{repeat } e \ c_{ev}, \Sigma \Downarrow_c (n, \text{cond}, \text{cond}), \Sigma''} \end{array}$$

Related functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{uint}(bv) &= \text{two's complement unsigned integer interpretation of } bv \\ \text{int}(bv) &= \text{two's complement integer interpretation of } bv \end{aligned}$$

Conditions progress on events. When some condition progresses to \checkmark , it means the condition is fully satisfied.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{onEvent}(\eta, (\sigma, \sigma')) &= \text{isRelevant}(\eta, (\sigma, \sigma')) ? \checkmark : \eta, \\ \text{onEvent}(\eta, id'_{ev}) &= \text{isRelevant}(\eta, id'_{ev}) ? \checkmark : \eta, \\ \text{onEvent}(t_\Delta, t) &= t \geq t_\Delta ? \checkmark : \eta, \\ \text{onEvent}((n, \text{cond}, \text{cond}'), ev) &= (\text{cond}'' = \checkmark) ? (n - 1 = 0 ? \checkmark : (n - 1, \text{cond}, \text{cond}')) \\ &\quad : (n, \text{cond}, \text{cond}''), \text{ where } \text{onEvent}(\text{cond}', ev) = \text{cond}'', \\ \text{onEvent}(\text{cond}, ev) &= \text{cond}, \text{ otherwise.} \end{aligned}$$

Related functions:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{isRelevant}(\eta, (\sigma, \sigma')) &= \begin{cases} \text{isRelevant}(\eta_1, (\sigma, \sigma')) \vee \text{isRelevant}(\eta_2, (\sigma, \sigma')) & \eta = \eta_1 \text{ or } \eta_2 \\ (\text{lsb}(\llbracket e \rrbracket \sigma), \text{lsb}(\llbracket e \rrbracket \sigma')) \in E_p & \eta = \text{posedge } e \\ (\text{lsb}(\llbracket e \rrbracket \sigma), \text{lsb}(\llbracket e \rrbracket \sigma')) \in E_n & \eta = \text{negedge } e \\ \llbracket e \rrbracket \sigma \neq \llbracket e \rrbracket \sigma' & \eta = e \\ \text{false} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \text{isRelevant}(\eta, id'_{ev}) &= \begin{cases} \text{isRelevant}(\eta_1, id'_{ev}) \vee \text{isRelevant}(\eta_2, id'_{ev}) & \eta = \eta_1 \text{ or } \eta_2 \\ \text{true} & \eta = id'_{ev} \\ \text{false} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \llbracket e \rrbracket \sigma &= \begin{cases} v & e, \sigma \rightarrow^* v, \sigma' \\ \perp & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

where $\text{lsb}(v)$ returns the least significant bit of v if v is a bit vector, and E_p and E_n are edge sets that define all possible posedges and negedges. For a two-value bit, $E_p = \{(0, 1)\}$ and $E_n = \{(1, 0)\}$. For a four-value bit, $E_p = \{(0, 1), (0, x), (0, z), (x, 1), (z, 1)\}$ and $E_n = \{(1, 0), (1, x), (1, z), (x, 0), (z, 0)\}$.

A.7.2 Synchronization

$$\frac{c, \Sigma \Downarrow_c \text{cond}, \Sigma' \quad pid = \text{newId}() \quad \beta' = \Sigma'.\beta[pid \mapsto \text{cond}]}{c \ s, \Sigma \hookrightarrow (\text{blocked } pid; s), \Sigma'[\beta \mapsto \beta']}$$

$$\frac{c, \Sigma \Downarrow_c \checkmark, \Sigma'}{c \ s, \Sigma \hookrightarrow s, \Sigma'}$$

$$\frac{pid \notin \text{keys}(\beta)}{\text{blocked } pid, \beta \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \beta}$$

$$\frac{}{\rightarrow id_{ev}, \beta, u_{nb} \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \text{activate}(\beta, id_{ev}), \text{trigger}(u_{nb}, id_{ev})}$$

A.8 Flow Control Statement

A.8.1 Sequential and Parallel Composition

$$\frac{}{\text{skip}; s \hookrightarrow s} \quad \frac{}{\text{skip} \parallel s \hookrightarrow s} \quad \frac{}{s \parallel \text{skip} \hookrightarrow s}$$

A.8.2 If and While

$$\frac{\text{isTrue}(v)}{\text{if } v \text{ then } s_1 \text{ else } s_2 \hookrightarrow s_1}, \quad \frac{\neg \text{isTrue}(v)}{\text{if } v \text{ then } s_1 \text{ else } s_2 \hookrightarrow s_2}$$

$\text{isTrue}(v)$ is satisfied if and only if the v is a nonzero known value, i.e., it is not a zero value and does not contain a **x** or **z** bit. We introduce this auxiliary function to make our rules more concise.

$$\frac{}{\text{while } e \text{ then } s \hookrightarrow \text{if } e \text{ then } (s; \text{while } e \text{ then } s) \text{ else skip}}$$

A.8.3 Control Operators

$$\frac{label \notin \text{keys}(\ell)}{label \ s, \ell \hookrightarrow s \text{ with } label, \ell[label \mapsto 1]}$$

$$\frac{label \in \text{keys}(\ell)}{label \ s, \ell \hookrightarrow s \text{ with } label, \ell[label \mapsto \ell(label) + 1]}$$

$$\frac{label \notin \text{keys}(\ell)}{s \text{ with } label, \ell \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \ell}$$

$$\frac{label \in \text{keys}(\ell) \quad s, \Sigma \rightarrow s', \Sigma'}{s \text{ with } label, \Sigma \hookrightarrow s' \text{ with } label, \Sigma'}$$

$$\frac{label \in \text{keys}(\ell) \quad \ell(label) = 1}{\text{skip with } label, \ell \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \text{delKey}(\ell, label)}$$

$$\frac{label \in \text{keys}(\ell) \quad \ell(label) > 1}{\text{skip with } label, \ell \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \ell[label \mapsto \ell(label) - 1]}$$

$$\frac{}{\text{disable } label, \ell \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \text{delKey}(\ell, label)}$$

$$\text{delKey}(m, k) = \{(k' \mapsto v) \mid (k' \mapsto v) \in m \wedge k \neq k'\}$$

A.9 Assignment

A.9.1 Blocking Assignment

$$\frac{}{v_l = c \ v \ \hookrightarrow \ c \ v_l = v}$$

$$\frac{v_r = \text{resolve}(v_l, v, \alpha, \kappa, \sigma) \quad v_r = \text{load}(\sigma, v_l)}{v_l = v, \sigma \ \hookrightarrow \ \mathbf{skip}, \sigma}$$

$$\frac{v_r = \text{resolve}(v_l, v, \alpha, \kappa, \sigma) \quad v_r \neq \text{load}(\sigma, v_l) \quad \sigma' = \text{store}(\sigma, v_l, v_r) \quad \beta' = \text{activate}(\beta, (\sigma, \sigma')) \quad u'_{nb} = \text{trigger}(u_{nb}, (\sigma, \sigma'))}{v_l = v, \sigma, \beta, u_{nb}, \text{sig} \ \hookrightarrow \ \mathbf{skip}, \sigma', \beta', u'_{nb}, \text{sig} \cup \text{signal}(\alpha, v_l)}$$

$\text{resolve}(v_l, v, \alpha, \kappa, \sigma)$ resolves possible multiple drivers (from procedural continuous assignments) for v_l by the following steps:

1. collects v_l 's driving values by a $\text{drVals}(v_l, \sigma, \alpha)$ function,
2. resolves those driving values according to resolve functions that are different for nets and variables,
3. and finally override the resolved driving value to v_l 's current value v to get the result v_r .

Because the formalization of the whole $\text{resolve}()$'s implementation is rather verbose and uninteresting, we just list some key points. Please refer to our artifact [2] for detailed implementation.

The $\text{drVals}()$ is the key function used during the resolution process, and it is defined as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{drVals}(v_l, \sigma, \alpha) &= \{(v_l', \sigma(\text{aid}), pr) : \text{aid} \in \text{drivers}(v_l, \alpha) \\ &\quad \wedge \text{aid} \in \text{keys}(\sigma) \wedge \alpha(\text{aid}) = (v_l', -, -, pr)\} \\ \text{drivers}(v_l, \alpha) &= \{\text{aid} \in \text{keys}(\alpha) : \alpha(\text{aid}) = (v_l', -, -, -) \wedge \text{overlap}(v_l, v_l')\} \end{aligned}$$

The $\text{overlap}()$ function decides whether two left values have their targets overlapped. We omit its formal definition.

$\text{load}()$ and $\text{store}()$ are defined as below:

$$\text{load}(\sigma, v_l) = \begin{cases} \sigma(id) & v_l = id \\ \text{select}(\sigma(id), v_1, v_2) & v_l = id[v_1:v_2] \\ \sigma(id)(v_i) & v_l = id[v_i] \\ \text{select}(\sigma(id)(v_i), v_1, v_2) & v_l = id[v_i][v_1:v_2] \end{cases}$$

$$\text{store}(\sigma, v_l, v) = \begin{cases} \sigma[id \mapsto v] & v_l = id \\ \sigma[id \mapsto \text{selectSet}(\sigma(id), v_1, v_2, v)] & v_l = id[v_1:v_2] \\ \sigma[id \mapsto \sigma(id)[v_i \mapsto v]] & v_l = id[v_i] \\ \sigma[id \mapsto \sigma(id)[v_i \mapsto \text{selectSet}(\sigma(id)(v_i), v_1, v_2, v)]] & v_l = id[v_i][v_1:v_2] \end{cases}$$

The function $\text{select}(x, c, d)$ implements the semantics of Verilog expression $\mathbf{x}[c:d]$ and the function $\text{selectSet}(x, c, d, v)$ is semantically equivalent to the code snippet: `tmp = x; tmp[c:d] = v; return tmp.`

Functions related to the activate() are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{activate}(\beta, ev) &= \{pid \mapsto cond \mid pid \in \text{keys}(\beta) \wedge cond = \text{onEvent}(\beta(pid), ev)\} \\ \text{trigger}(u_{nb}, ev) &= \begin{cases} \epsilon & u_{nb} = \epsilon \\ (v_l, v, \text{onEvent}(cond, ev)) \text{ ++ } \text{trigger}(u'_{nb}, ev) & u_{nb} = (v_l, v, cond) \text{ ++ } u'_{nb} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Functions related to the signal are defined as follows:

$$\text{signal}(\alpha, v_l) = \{aid \in \text{keys}(\alpha) : \alpha(aid) = (-, e, -, -) \wedge \text{sensitive}(e, v_l)\}$$

where $\text{sensitive}(e, v_l)$ decides whether e is sensitive to v_l , i.e, the value of e will be changed if v_l changes. It can be defined approximately by allowing false positives (because re-computation of an unchanged e for some assign item does not affect the final result):

$$\text{sensitive}(e, v_l) = \text{ID}(v_l) \in \text{use}(e) \setminus \text{def}(e)$$

where the $\text{ID}(v_l)$ extracts the identifier in v_l . The $\text{use}(e)$ function returns all identifiers used in e and especially, for a do-return expression, the identifiers occurring on the right-hand side of its statements. The $\text{def}(e)$ function returns a non-empty set if and only if e is a do-return expression and the non-empty set contains all the identifiers occurring on the left-hand side of statements in e .

A.9.2 Nonblocking Assignment

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{v_l \Leftarrow v, u_{nb} \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, u_{nb} \text{ ++ } (v_l, v, \checkmark)}{c, \Sigma \Downarrow_c cond, \Sigma' \quad \frac{u'_{nb} = \Sigma'.u_{nb} \text{ ++ } (v_l, v, cond)}{v_l \Leftarrow c v, \Sigma \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \Sigma'[u_{nb} \mapsto u'_{nb}]} \\ & \frac{\text{hasActive}(u_{nb})}{s, u_{nb} \xrightarrow{nb} (s \parallel \text{peekActive}(u_{nb}), \text{delActive}(u_{nb}))} \\ \text{hasActive}(u_{nb}) &= \begin{cases} \text{false} & u_{nb} = \epsilon \\ cond = \checkmark \vee \text{hasActive}(u'_{nb}) & u_{nb} = (v_l, v, cond) \text{ ++ } u'_{nb} \end{cases} \\ \text{peekActive}(u_{nb}) &= \begin{cases} \text{skip} & u_{nb} = \epsilon \\ v_l = v; \text{peekActive}(u'_{nb}) & u_{nb} = (v_l, v, \checkmark) \text{ ++ } u'_{nb} \\ \text{peekActive}(u'_{nb}) & u_{nb} = (v_l, v, cond) \text{ ++ } u'_{nb} \end{cases} \\ \text{delActive}(u_{nb}) &= \begin{cases} \epsilon & u_{nb} = \epsilon \\ \text{delActive}(u'_{nb}) & u_{nb} = (v_l, v, \checkmark) \text{ ++ } u'_{nb} \\ (v_l, v, cond) \text{ ++ } \text{delActive}(u'_{nb}) & u_{nb} = (v_l, v, cond) \text{ ++ } u'_{nb} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

A.9.3 Continuous Assignment

$$\frac{sig = sig' \cup \{aid\} \quad aid \notin \text{keys}(\alpha)}{\alpha, sig \rightarrow \alpha, sig'}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\Sigma.sig = sig' \cup \{aid\} \quad aid \in \text{keys}(\Sigma.\alpha) \quad \Sigma' = \Sigma[sig \mapsto sig'] \\
\Sigma'.\alpha(aid) = (v_l, e, \perp, pr) \quad e, \Sigma' \rightarrow^* v, \Sigma'' \\
u''_\alpha = \Sigma''.u_\alpha[aid \mapsto (v_l, v, \checkmark)] \\
\hline
\Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma''[u_\alpha \mapsto u''_\alpha] \\
\\
\Sigma.sig = sig' \cup \{aid\} \quad aid \in \text{keys}(\Sigma.\alpha) \quad \Sigma' = \Sigma[sig \mapsto sig'] \\
\Sigma'.\alpha(aid) = (v_l, e, c, pr) \quad e, \Sigma' \rightarrow^* v, \Sigma'' \quad c, \Sigma'' \Downarrow_c cond, \Sigma''' \\
u''_\alpha = \Sigma'''.u_\alpha[aid \mapsto (v_l, v, cond)] \\
\hline
\Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma'''[u_\alpha \mapsto u''_\alpha] \\
\\
u_\alpha = u'_\alpha \cup \{aid \mapsto (v_l, v, \checkmark)\} \quad aid \notin \text{keys}(\alpha) \vee v = \sigma(aid) \\
\sigma, \alpha, u_\alpha \rightarrow \sigma, \alpha, u'_\alpha \\
\\
u_\alpha = u'_\alpha \cup \{aid \mapsto (v_l, v, \checkmark)\} \quad aid \in \text{keys}(\alpha) \quad v \neq \sigma(aid) \\
\sigma' = \sigma[aid \mapsto v] \quad v_r = \text{resolve}(v_l, \text{load}(\sigma', v_l), \sigma', \kappa, \alpha) \\
\sigma'' = \text{store}(\sigma', v_l, v_r) \quad \beta' = \text{activate}(\beta, (\sigma, \sigma'')) \quad u'_{nb} = \text{trigger}(u_{nb}, (\sigma, \sigma'')) \\
\hline
\sigma, \beta, u_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha, u_\alpha, sig \rightarrow \sigma'', \beta', u'_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha, u'_\alpha, sig \cup \text{signal}(\alpha, v_l)
\end{array}$$

where the $\text{resolve}()$ function has been defined before.

A.9.4 Procedural Continuous Assignment

$$\begin{array}{c}
id = \text{ID}(v_l) \\
\text{deassign } v_l \text{ with } pr, \sigma, \beta, u_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha, sig \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \sigma', \beta', u'_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha', sig' \\
aid = \text{newId}() \quad \alpha'' = \alpha'[aid \mapsto (v_l, e, \perp, pr)] \quad sig'' = sig \cup \{aid\} \\
\hline
\text{assign } v_l = e \text{ with } pr, \sigma, \beta, u_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha, sig \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \sigma', \beta', u'_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha', sig'' \\
\alpha' = \text{deassign}(\alpha, v_l, pr) \quad id = \text{ID}(v_l) \quad v_r = \text{resolve}(id, \sigma(id), \sigma, \kappa, \alpha') \quad v_r = \sigma(id) \\
\hline
\text{deassign } v_l \text{ with } pr, \sigma, \kappa, \alpha \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \sigma, \kappa, \alpha' \\
\alpha' = \text{deassign}(\alpha, v_l, pr) \quad id = \text{ID}(v_l) \quad v_r = \text{resolve}(id, \sigma(id), \sigma, \kappa, \alpha') \quad v_r \neq \sigma(id) \\
\sigma' = \sigma[id \mapsto v_r] \quad \beta' = \text{activate}(\beta, (\sigma, \sigma')) \\
u'_{nb} = \text{trigger}(u_{nb}, (\sigma, \sigma')) \quad sig' = sig \cup \text{signal}(\alpha', id) \\
\hline
\text{deassign } v_l \text{ with } pr, \sigma, \beta, u_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha, sig \hookrightarrow \text{skip}, \sigma', \beta', u'_{nb}, \kappa, \alpha', sig'
\end{array}$$

The $\text{deassign}()$ function is implemented as below:

$$\text{deassign}(\alpha, v_l, pr) = \{aid \mapsto \alpha(aid) \mid aid \in \text{keys}(\alpha) \wedge \neg(\alpha(aid) = (v_l', \rightarrow, \rightarrow, pr) \wedge \text{overlap}(v_l, v_l'))\}$$

Note that when implementing the $\text{deassign}()$ function, you had better delete those deassigned aid from σ as well. Otherwise, there would be memory leaks.

A.10 Time Advancement

$$\begin{array}{c}
t' = t + \Delta \quad \beta' = \text{activate}(\beta, t') \\
u'_{nb} = \text{trigger}(u_{nb}, t') \quad u'_\alpha = \text{trigger}(u_\alpha, t') \quad (\beta, u_{nb}, u_\alpha, t) \neq (\beta', u'_{nb}, u'_\alpha, t') \\
\hline
\beta, u_{nb}, u_\alpha, t \xrightarrow{\Delta} \beta', u'_{nb}, u'_\alpha, t'
\end{array}$$

where

$$\text{trigger}(u_\alpha, ev) = \{aid \mapsto (v_l, v, \text{onEvent}(cond, ev)) \mid u_\alpha(aid) = (v_l, v, cond)\}$$

References

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